

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOTIVATION FOR LEARNING IN TURKMEN AND RUSSIAN STUDENTS

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***Abstract.** One of the important problems in modern education is the formation of motivation among students. The relevance of this problem can be explained by the fact that it is necessary to update the content of training, to develop in students knowledge and skills that will help them develop their personality and develop their active life position. The biggest problems that exist in the field of education are associated, first of all, with the lack of motivation for getting an education among the majority of students, which leads to a decrease in the main indicators of education and upbringing of graduates; the importance of this criterion becomes obvious. Learning activities are activities that have completely different meanings for different students. Despite this, it is necessary to identify the motivation for each student for each student, it is necessary that each student understands why he needs education. It is the nature of educational motivation that plays a big role for the teacher, since depending on the nature of motivation, the teacher chooses all pedagogical measures of influence that will be relevant in this case.*

***Keywords:** character, knowledge, psychological and pedagogical, values, motivation, psychological reasons.*

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is considered in psychological and pedagogical literature as a set of psychological reasons that explain human behavior, its direction and activity.

If we consider the scientific literature, we can distinguish five main blocks of motivation. Let's look at them in more detail:

1. Personal motivation. In this case, we can say that each person has his own ideals, values, as well as how he absorbs information from the environment.

Personal meaning of learning may consist of:

- understanding the significance of training from an objective point of view;
- understanding why he personally needs training.

2. Types of learning motives:

- external;
- informative;
- internal;
- social;
- motives for achieving success;
- motives for avoiding failure.

3. Setting goals. It is very important for motivation to be able to set goals correctly and clearly.

4. Be able to implement motivation in your behavior. The following aspects of motivation can be noted:

- attention to the extent to which motives actually influence educational activities and the child's behavior;
- how important motivation is and how it affects different types of activities;
- mastery of academic subjects;
- selection of forms of educational tasks.

5. The emotional component of learning motivation, that is, the student's emotional attitude towards learning.

The personal meaning of learning can be defined as the student's internal subjective attitude towards the educational process. During learning, a student cannot automatically understand the meaning of learning itself, nor will he be able to automatically understand the role of learning for him. During training, the teacher must form such aspirations that will contribute to the study of new topics and the pursuit of knowledge. The personal meaning of learning varies from person to person. It depends on the age of the students, on their character and on their personality. The content of training and the methods that are used must be selected taking into account the group of students who are being trained. These methods must fully meet the meaning of teaching a group of students [Apasova, M.V-2020].

The meaning of learning for each student is, first of all, determined by their ideals and values that they set for themselves. In addition, the meaning of learning is influenced by what surrounds the student. Thanks to all this, even before the learning process begins, the future student forms his own opinion regarding educational activities. But it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that very often the learning process itself and the ideas that develop are different.

Let's note the main points that make up the meaning of training:

- student awareness of the objective significance of learning, which is determined by the moral values developed in society and accepted in the social environment and in the family of the child;
- understanding the importance of learning for oneself, which is necessarily refracted through the level of the student's aspirations, his self-control and self-esteem of educational work, its individual connections.

When considering Learning Motivation, it is necessary to take into account that there are three approaches that help determine groups of motives [Aseev.V.G.-2016].

In the first case, all motives are divided into two large groups. The first group of motives is social. The second group of motives are cognitive.

Cognitive motives of education are those motives that are directly related to the educational process and learning activities. These motives are aimed at ensuring that students acquire new knowledge, better assimilate the material and develop an interest in learning. This also includes motives that indicate the focus and mastery of methods through which students gain knowledge:

- interest in methods of independent acquisition of knowledge,
- interest in methods of scientific knowledge,
- interest in methods of self-regulation of educational work,
- interest in the rational organization of one's own educational work. This group of motives contributes to the fact that students have an interest in self-improvement, in acquiring new knowledge and in self-education.

The second group of motives discussed above are social motives. They are primarily related to interaction between people. Let's look at this with an example. Some students enroll in higher

education because they want to fulfill their duty, because they want to be useful to society or simply out of a sense of responsibility. In addition, as an example of social motives, we can note those motives that are associated with the desire to take a certain position in society or gain some kind of authority or respect in society. Social motives are closely related to attempts to assert oneself, take the place of a leader, dominate the team, and so on.

The motives of social cooperation indicate that the student wants to interact with other people who surround him, strives to understand them, so the hedgehog constantly analyzes the ways of his communication with others, that is, the teacher, classmates, and so on. These motives are a very important part, which helps an individual to improve himself and promotes self-education [Aseev.V.G.-2016]

Students who want to succeed most often attribute their failures to the amount of effort they put in. This suggests that they have an internal controlling factor. If a student very often tries to avoid possible failures, then he most often explains this by the lack of any ability or simply bad luck. In this case, you can notice differences in the approach, which is called “learned helplessness.”

The student understands that he cannot in any way influence what the complexity of the task will be, whether there will be luck, whether he will have enough knowledge to solve the task, so he believes that solving the task is pointless and does not try to take any action. Very often, such students refuse to complete tasks at all, even the simplest ones. This suggests that the teacher must develop the desire for success in his students; it is necessary to ensure that the desire for success prevails over the desire to prevent possible failure [Bakshaev.N.A. - 2016].

How well and efficiently the motives will be realized depends on how well students are able to set goals for themselves, how well they can justify them and achieve them.

Motives and goals may differ in content. If we apply this concept to the educational process, then students should set themselves the goal of completing certain tasks, which the teacher gives. The goal should be focused on the intermediate result of educational activities.

Motives will be effective if they have personal meaning. In this case, the motive will be implemented in the student’s behavior. This will be expressed in the student’s initiative, in his activity. In this case, the student will easily and with great pleasure complete all the tasks that the teacher will offer. In addition, if the student has a personal meaning, he will try to gain more knowledge, that is, he will study additionally and gain new knowledge that will be useful to him in the future [Bakshaev.N.A. - 2016].

The emotional component in motivation is of great importance. The emotional attitude towards learning and what emotions the student experiences while studying plays a big role in mastering the material.

What emotions a student will experience during his studies is directly related to what emotions he experiences in class, what emotions he experiences at the university. These emotions can depend on various factors:

- depends on the relationship between the student and the teacher,
- how the student participates in the life of the team,
- the absence or presence of various conflicts with classmates,
- to what extent the student realizes his potential,
- how well the student knows how to overcome the difficulties he encounters.

Thus, learning motivation is considered as a set of motives aimed at students acquiring knowledge; the motivational sphere of students undergoes various changes in the learning process. The mutual influence of motives and learning goals occurs constantly - the student experiences the birth of new learning motives, which contribute to the emergence of new goals.

Motivation has been studied by many psychologists, so modern psychological science presents a wide range of its interpretations. Thus, A.K. Markova understands the motives of learning as the student's orientation towards various aspects of educational activity. All this suggests that motives can be of two types: cognitive and social. Cognitive motives are directly related to the content of learning. Social motives relate to how a student interacts with teachers and other students. Psychologists distinguish positive and negative motivation, as well as stable and situational motives [Bychkova, L.A. - 2021].

In the works of P. Ya. Galperin, V. V. Davydov, D. B. Elkonin and N. F. Talyzin one can find the so-called activity theory of learning. According to the authors, this is a method that helps to more fully understand what motivation is.

Any type of motivation has its pros and cons. Likewise, external motivation has its pros and cons. It's no secret that competitive and prestigious motivations are widespread in high school, and they are very good, since they give good learning results.

There is such a type of motivation as competitive. This type of motivation has become widespread in high school. At this age, children do not want to lag behind each other, but want to have a result that will be better than that of their classmates.

Cognitive motive should be formed at a young age, it begins to form in elementary school. D. B. Elkonin is a famous school psychologist who created a system of education and in his works described how it is necessary to form educational activities in children of primary school age. In his works, D. B. Elkonin says that the motives for such activity can be not only those activities that are associated with education, but also those activities that are associated with cognition.

Cognitive activity begins at the beginning of a student's school life, and it changes over time. That is, the cognitive motives of a first-grader and the school will be different. A.K. Markov in his works described three stages or three levels of cognitive motivation in schoolchildren. In his opinion, the first stage is a broad cognitive motive, which is aimed at students gaining new knowledge. At the second level, an educational and cognitive motive appears, which stimulates children to acquire new knowledge. And the last third level is self-education [Bychkova, L.A. - 2021].

If we consider the ideal picture, it looks like this. Students entering school have cognitive motives. As they get older, they become more focused on what skills they are learning, how well they are learning. At an older age, that is, in high school, they should strive to educate themselves. If we consider the situation in practice, it is a little different. Students begin to develop cognitive motives only in the fifth to eighth grade.

D. B. Elkonin says that the position that schoolchildren have is that they need to attend classes, do homework and listen to what the teacher says. This position is typical for a person who improves himself. Many scientists who have studied this topic say that in order to organize correct and successful educational activities, it is necessary to ensure that all its components develop [Kozulina, A.P., -2015].

Psychologists from the school of P. Ya. Galperin conducted a study, as a result of which it became clear that the nature of motivation directly depends on what type of training is used. In

addition, the nature of motivation depends on the material being studied, the role of the student in the lesson and the type of training [Kozulina, A.P. -2015]. The teacher sets different tasks for the student in class, during which the child acquires new skills and also acquires new knowledge. In this case, memorizing new material is a natural consequence of learning, since there is no need to specifically remember anything. The main advantage of P. Ya. Galperin's theory is the possibility of its practical application. In some Russian cities, such as Bryansk and Orel, special teacher retraining centers have been created. It is noted that after training, teachers independently rebuild the system of teaching their subject [Bychkova, L.A. - 2021].

Thus, existing theoretical approaches to the study of student learning motivation are based on cognitive and social motives, but it cannot be said that the use of other motives in the formation of learning motivation is definitely bad. The formation of learning motivation is based on the theory of higher mental functions of the human psyche and the theory of activity in the development of a child's personality.

CONCLUSION

Thanks to the developed program, which includes activities aimed at the value of higher education and its subjectivization in educational activities, students will be motivated to actualize the importance of acquiring knowledge, and not just obtaining a diploma of higher education. also, due to the implemented program, there will be a smoother adaptation of students to the sociocultural characteristics of the country.

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